

PERSONAL INCOME TAX AND MEASURES TO FURTHER IMPROVE IT

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Abstract. This article analyzes the current state of the income tax system in Uzbekistan from individuals and the directions of its further reform. It provides detailed information about the structure of tax rates, the basic principles of taxation, as well as changes and updates that are being implemented in the tax system. Key approaches and strategies used in the reform process are highlighted, including the introduction of digital technologies, streamlining of tax rates, and benefits and reliefs aimed at taxpayers.

Keywords: Individuals, income tax, tax reform, tax rates, digital technologies, tax incentives, economic development, tax system, tax updates.

Introduction: The role of the tax system in the economic and social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is important. The tax system serves as the main tool in ensuring the financial stability of the state. Income tax from individuals, on the other hand, is the most important component of this system. This type of tax is one of the main sources of revenue for the state budget and plays a key role in financing the social protection system.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has undergone a number of reforms on the tax

system, in particular on income tax from individuals. According to the current tax code of Uzbekistan, income tax from individuals is not based on progressive tax rates, which means that the tax rate will not increase either with an increase in income. These tax rates are determined by the annual clean income of individuals and cover various sources of income, including wages, income from independent activities, capital income, etc.

These reforms are aimed at optimizing tax rates, clearly establishing the rights and obligations of taxpayers, as well as making the tax system more transparent and effective. These reforms, together with the creation of favorable conditions for taxpayers, are carried out in order to expand the tax base and increase the revenues of the state budget.

This introductory part of the article covers the current state of the system of income tax on individuals in Uzbekistan and the directions of its further reform. Detailed information will be provided about the approaches used in the reform process of the tax system, the basic principles of taxation, as well as the problems faced in this process and their solutions.

Literature Review:

The following studies on income tax on individuals and its reform are important in Uzbekistan:

"Economic impact of tax reform in Uzbekistan" - this study analyzes how tax reforms in Uzbekistan have affected economic growth. The study studies the changes in tax policies and their impact on macroeconomic indicators such as production, investment and consumption.

"Comparison of international tax systems, on the example of Uzbekistan"

- in this study, Uzbekistan compares the tax system with the tax systems of other countries, including developed and developing countries. The aim is to identify best practices and offer potential reform directions for Uzbekistan.

"Tax Policy and social stability, analysis of Uzbekistan" - in this study, studies

the economic and social consequences of tax policy for representatives of different segments of the population, in particular the low-income and middle class. The study analyzes how tax relief and benefits can contribute to social stability.

” Advantages and problems of digital taxation, in the context of Uzbekistan ” - this study examines the advantages and problems faced by the implementation of the digital taxation system in Uzbekistan. The study suggests ways to improve the effectiveness, transparency and user accessibility of digital taxation.

” Tax policy, international practices and local applications for persons not living in Uzbekistan ” - this study examines the international practices of tax policy for persons not living in Uzbekistan and tries to identify strategies suitable for Uzbekistan.

In the above studies, it provides a scientific basis and practical recommendations for further improvement of Uzbekistan's tax system, however, the rapid development of the country's economy by the time requires the implementation of new research work.

Methodology:

The methodological approach of the article relies on information from various sources in order to ensure accurate and objective results of the analysis. For this analysis, the following steps were carried out:

Data collection:

To collect information about the tax system and its reforms, the sources of official tax legislation of Uzbekistan, in particular the tax code, and international tax analysis, were considered.

Data was collected on income tax rates, dividends, and interest tax rates for living and non-living individuals.

Public and private sector sources as well as academic research have been studied for socio-economic impact analysis.

Data analysis:

Based on the data collected, the dynamics of tax rates and their economic impact were analyzed.

How tax rates are applied depending on different sources of income and the category of individuals, and the consequences of this application were assessed.

The impact of tax policies and reforms on the country's economy and the activities of international investors was analyzed.

Dialogue with experts:

Expert interviews were conducted on Tax Policy and its economic consequences. These conversations gave a deeper understanding of tax rates and their practices, and increased the reliability of the analysis.

The opinions and experiences of industry experts, as well as their proposals for the adoption of tax reforms, were taken into account.

Data integration and report creation:

A complete and accurate report was prepared based on the collected and analyzed data. The report detailed the current state of the tax system, the processes of its reform and its future plans.

The report also included conclusions and recommendations on the economic and social consequences of tax policy.

This methodological approach made it possible to deeply and comprehensively cover the content of the article, which will help readers fully understand the tax on income from individuals in Uzbekistan and its economic significance.

Analysis and Results

Of the tax code (henceforth referred to as -SK.)

Article 364 is about taxpayers who are told:

- 1) individuals who are residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- 2) includes individuals who are non-residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan who receive income from sources in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

In article SK 365, the object of taxation is the object of taxation of the taxpayer's total income. According to SK article 366, the tax base is as follows:

- Total income for individuals who are residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the tax benefits provided for by the tax code;

- Total income for individuals who are non-residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the absence of the application of tax benefits provided for in the tax code.

- When determining the tax base, the rights of the taxpayer arising for the disposal of income or income received both in the form of money and in kind are taken into account, as well as income in the form of material benefit.

In this case, the income of a particular type of taxpayer may or may not be taken into account in the structure of the total income under the conditions and procedure established by the tax code.

The taxpayer's income, expressed in foreign currency, is actually recalculated into the national currency at the exchange rate of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the date of receipt of income.

The tax base on different tax rates is determined separately. The tax base is determined by the growing end from the beginning of the tax period.

If deductions are made from the taxpayer's income according to his own order, the decision of the court or other bodies and organizations, such deductions will not reduce the tax base.

The total income of individuals includes:

- 1) income in the form of remuneration for Labor;
- 2) property income;
- 3) income in the style of material benefit;
- 4) other income.

Income in the form of remuneration is all payments (wages, premiums, surcharges, compensation, etc.) that are calculated and paid to employees who are

in a labor - related relationship with the employer and are performing work in accordance with the concluded employment contract.) are recognized as income in the form of remuneration.

Property income is-interest payments to the property income of individuals, dividends, income from the rental of property, income from the sale of property and other income.

Income in the form of material benefit is - the payment by the tax agent of goods (services) in the interests of the taxpayer, property rights, amounts written off by the decision of a legal entity of an individual's debt to the tax agent, etc.k.

Other income is this-other income of individuals is felt. Benefits to taxpayers by citizens ' self-government, charitable and environmental funds, as well as assistance in other types;

Revenues from the sale of animals (cattle, poultry, furs and other animals, fish, etc.) alive and slaughtered them and their products raw or processed, and the sale of silkworm, livestock, beekeeping and agricultural products in natural and processed form;

The value of property, property rights received from individuals for free (including under gift agreements) ;

Prizes, cash prizes awarded for prizes in competitions, reviews, competitions; Achievements;

Sums of grants received from the grantor, including grants from foreign countries;

Income of taxpayers for created works of science, literature and art (subjects) ;

One-way prize money that athletes receive for winning prizes in international sports competitions;

Severance benefits and other payments made in accordance with labor legislation when the employment contract (contract) concluded with the employee

is terminated;

Material assistance provided as follows: provided to family members of a deceased employee or to an employee in connection with the death of a family member;

Indicated to the employee in connection with the fact that he was crippled in labor, occupational disease or otherwise injured in his health;

Indicated in connection with the birth of a child, the marriage of an employee or his children;

Material assistance provided in the manner of providing agricultural products or providing funds for their purchase;

Payments made to non-working pensioners by a tax agent;

paid payments for the compensation of moral damage;

income received due to correction of prices in cases and in the procedure established by Section VI of the tax code;

income received under the contract of waiver of the right of claim in favor of the other, which is determined in the manner provided for by Article 300 of the tax code;

Other income of the taxpayer not specified in articles 371-376 of the tax code.

Table 1:

Comparative rates of income tax from individuals:

Minimum monthly wage rate	2014	2015	2016-2017	2018	2020-2024 years
1 equal		0%	0%	0%	12 %*
2 equal	7,5%	8,5%	7,5%	7,5%	

3 equal				
4 equal				
5 equal				
6 equal				
7 equal				
8 equal				
9 equal				
10 equal	16%	17%	17%	16,5%
More than 10 equal	22%	23%	23%	22,5%

Results:

As a result of this tax policy analysis, the following main conclusions can be drawn:

The following table of population income records an increase in employment relative to employment-i.e. if the employment rate is 15% at the highest level on 1

December 2017-on 1 December 2023 the rate was 7%.

Diagram 3. Minimum wage:

The minimum wage has only increased from 2017 to 2023. That is, in 2017 it was 174,240 soums, while in 2023 this figure amounted to 1,050,000 soums.

The procedure for calculating income tax from individuals is as follows:

Example 1. An individual received a salary of 1,000,000 soums in January.

Calculate income tax?

$$1,000,000 \times 12\% = 120,000 \text{ soums in income tax.}$$

Example 2. An individual received a salary of 1,000,000 soums in January, 500,000 soums in the form of dividends, and

634,880 soums in material assistance from the workplace (in the case of deceased family members). How much income tax is paid by an individual?

$$1,000,000 \times 12\% = 120,000 \text{ soums}$$

$$500,000 \times 5\% = 25,000 \text{ soums (Article 318, Part 2 of the Tax Code)}$$

Material assistance of 634,880 soums is not subject to tax in accordance with Article 378 of the Tax Code.

Therefore, the individual will pay a total of 145,000 soums (120,000+25,000) in income tax.

Conclusion:

1) progressive taxation: to continue to maintain or increase progressive tax rates in which higher earners are taxed at a higher rate than lower earners. This helps to redistribute wealth in a more equitable way and ensures that those with higher incomes contribute proportionally more.

2) tax credits and deductions: expanding or correcting tax credits and deductions for low and middle income earners. This may include loans for childcare, education costs, health care costs, or home ownership.

3) imparting peace to the hidden economy: regularly reviewing and taking control of loopholes that allow high-income individuals or corporations not to pay a fair share of taxes. This may include tightening regulations on tax shelters, offshore accounts, or corporate tax avoidance strategies.

4) simplification: to simplify the tax code to make it easier for individuals to understand and comply with their tax obligations. Reducing complexity can reduce administrative costs for both taxpayers and the government.

5) tax filing assistance: providing resources and assistance to help taxpayers manage the tax filing process, especially for those with low income or limited financial literacy. This can include free tax services, online document filing tools, or utilities.

6) indexation for inflation: adaptation of tax burdens and deductions for inflation to prevent individuals from being pushed into higher tax brackets due to inflationary growth of income without making appropriate adjustments to tax limits.

7) tax benefits for savings and investments: offering tax benefits to encourage savings for retirement, education or other long-term purposes. This includes tax credits on tax deferred retirement accounts, Education Fund account sheets, or

capital gains for certain investments.

8) transparency and accountability: increase transparency in the tax system to ensure taxpayers understand how their tax funds are being used and to hold policy makers accountable for their tax policy decisions.

9) combining environmental and social goals: consider adding tax incentives or penalties to promote environmentally sustainable behavior or address social problems such as the use of affordable housing or health services.

10) international cooperation: working in cooperation with other countries to solve problems related to tax evasion, transfer pricing and avoidance of international taxes. This may include the implementation of global tax standards or agreements to prevent the erosion of the tax base and changes in profits.

11) review and Evaluation: a systematic review of the effectiveness of tax policies and making adjustments as needed based on empirical evidence and stakeholder feedback.

In conclusion, the current tax policy of Uzbekistan and the measures taken to reform it will play an important role in the economic development of the country, and these changes are expected to continue in the future.

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